

A study on the correct value of tension for canvas paintings.

Antonio Iaccarino Idelson

Lecturer at University of Urbino, Italy

Scientific Consultant, Conservation Laboratory of the Province of Viterbo,

Conservator - Restorer in Equilibrarte S.r.l., Roma.

iaccarino.a@gmail.com

ABSTRACT.

The use of stretchers that provide controlled elastic tension while leaving the canvas free to move along the tacking margin results in an even distribution of tensions, despite dimensional changes caused by environmental factors. Quantification of the force becomes also possible, and this allows the comparison of experiences on the chosen value of tension, traditionally considered to be among the main conservation factors but hardly ever measured.

This paper presents the main results of an ongoing research based on the measurement of the effects of tension on the mechanical behaviour of paintings. Measurements are compared with the experience of a group of Conservators-Restorers, aiming at the definition of the correct value of tension for the tested paintings. An unexpected result has been the identification of a value defined as "Maximum Useful Tension". Beyond this, no significant improvement of the reaction of the painting to an external deforming force seems to correspond to a further rise of tension.

Development of stretchers along with the needs of conservation

The progressive loss of tension of the painting on its stretcher has been among the main conservation problems, and one of the first to become evident in a painting's history. It is due to the powerful tensions that environmental changes generate within its structure. Stress concentrations lead to distortions that, starting from the corner areas, can end up with the deformation of the whole painting and the instability of paint layers.

Though this has always been true, the second half of the 18th century¹ has seen the development of the key-expansion stretchers that we still use today: the corner joints were modified and the stretcher made stronger in order to be able to withstand the forces it imposes to the painting. This was due to the increasing care for conservation of ancient paintings, and to the change in the mechanisms of taste and perception that led to consider as intolerable any deformation of the support², within the needs of neoclassic sensibility.

¹ [32], page 55.

² As in: Capriotti, G. "Piano e superpiano come luogo della raffigurazione pittorica". In: [8].

About one century later, we see the development of a stretcher in which the corner keys have been substituted with springs³ that constantly push stretcher bars apart, in order to avoid the need of “keying out” the stretcher when relaxation occurred. This stretcher is based on the same principle as nowadays elastic expansion stretchers.

Unfortunately, all stretchers based on corner expansion with the canvas fixed onto the tacking margin have the same shortcoming that used to damage the painting on fixed stretchers: stress concentration in the corners. This means that it is impossible to avoid giving excessive solicitations to the corners, in order to give enough tension to the centre of the painting. Spring loaded corner expansion may be useful for conservation if the stretchers were able to reduce their size when exceeding tension in the painting occurs. This could be achieved with the use of very soft springs, and with corners left partially open in “normal” environmental conditions. Still, this very rarely occurs, because important forces are needed to overcome the resistance of painting’s corner areas for tension to reach the centre. The use of springs that are stronger than the painting leads to an expansion system that works as if it were a key-stretcher kept always at a very high tension.

Roberto Carità contributed to the evolution of the canvas paintings tensioning systems with a significant innovation right after the second world war, namely well before elastic stretchers started being as widespread as they are today. He worked at Istituto Centrale per il Restauro (ICR) during one of the most splendid moments of its history, between 1954 and 1960, and brought there his exceptional experience as Art Historian and Conservator, and his passion for mechanics⁴. While working at the Monuments and Fine Arts Office of Torino, he had been concerned with the re-contextualization of the works of art that had been sheltered during the war. Most of these works had been stored, and then restored, in extreme conditions. He had then had the possibility of “clearly understanding the violence of the solicitations a painting undergoes when nailed on a stretcher”. He therefore proposed [9], in collaboration with Paolo Mora and Giovanni Urbani, fixed stretchers with a smoothed and rounded profile in the place of the tacking margin, on which the canvas was allowed to move freely while being under a continuous tension obtained with a system of springs mounted on the rear of the stretcher, as shown in Figure 1.

³ Wright and Gardner. USA Patent of the 19 Jan. 1875, N. 159,012. Many patents based on the same principle have appeared since the end of the 19th century.

⁴ His most recent interview is published in [8] pages 137-144. Roberto Carità was in those years a real “alter ego” for Cesare Brandi, and was able to give a practical development to the aspects of his “Teoria del Restauro” that concerned the structural conservation of paintings (detached frescoes, canvas and panel paintings) and Museum display.

Figure 1: section of the stretcher designed by R. Carità for the “Beheading of the Baptist” by Caravaggio (from [9]). The canvas is free to flow on the rounded profile, and is kept in tension with the springs mounted on the crossbars.

Consequences of Roberto Carità’s work

The introduction of this principle brought an important change in force distribution within the painting, as it allowed avoiding stress concentration in the corners. This has been demonstrated in 1992 [2] with a Finite Elements Analysis (FEA) computer model, and the patterns of tension can be seen in Figure 2. Among the innovations descending from R. Carità’s work is the separation between the functions of tension and support of the painting: the stretcher supports the painting and the springs, while the latter are responsible for tension. In corner expansion stretchers support and tension are provided by the same structure, which needs to be rigid enough and at the same time allow dimensional changes acting at those points upon which rigidity is based. From this point of view, R. Carità made a silent revolution, that showed its fruits only some years later, from the ’80s onward: the following are some later applications based on the concepts he introduced.

Figure 2: comparison between the distribution of tensions in the top left corners of a key stretcher (left) and of the stretcher designed by R. Carità for the St. Jerome by Caravaggio (the red line is the stretcher, thus the canvas beyond the red line is folded on the rear). Illustrations courtesy of G. Accardo and M. Torre (Istituto Centrale per il Restauro, Rome), and G. Santucci (University of Rome, La Sapienza).

Gustav Berger published [4] in 1984 a tensioning system in which canvas flows on the rounded profiles of two opposite sides of the stretcher.

Franco Del Zotto in 1988 [15] proposed a solution in which perimetrical expansion of stretcher (actually made of two stretchers, the inner one of which is the structure that sustains the second, which moves outwards with spring loaded mechanisms) is combined with the movement of the canvas on flowing profiles.

The Istituto Centrale per il Restauro in 1991 [1] conserved R. Carità's stretcher for the "S. Jerome" by Caravaggio in Malta: the tensioning system is studied and restored, the rusted springs changed with new ones whose elastic constant is known and the force they produce is measured. In 1996, for applications on painted and gilded leather artefacts [23; 24], the study of the method went on, from the point of view of the elastic system⁵ and with the introduction of rolling profiles that minimize friction on the perimeter.

My contribution in 1996 [19] has been that of using the separation of the stretcher's functions in order to conserve original stretchers: these are modified with the addition of a low friction profile, and used only for the function of support. The elastic tensioning system, analogous to those made by R. Carità, is made with rather "soft" springs (low elastic constant), in order to minimize the variations of force due to dimensional changes. The value of the elastic constant of springs and the force chosen for the painting were stated in the paper.

The Opificio delle Pietre Dure in 1996 [12; 7; 11] introduced some variations to the system with an oscillating profile and springs placed on the side of the stretcher, even though this took place with the restoration of the "Beheading of the Baptist" by Caravaggio (Figure 1) and then with the sacrifice of one of the first Carità's stretchers [9].

⁵ For applications with leather, it is particularly important to have springs with a low elastic constant, in order to allow the artefact to do ample movements without significant variations of the tension.

The Restoration Laboratory of the Province of Viterbo has started a research on the subject in 2001⁶, and since then many original stretchers were conserved as rigid core of an elastic tensioning system. New experimental tensioning systems have been developed, both for canvas paintings and for banners.

Equilibrarte s.r.l., a company I started in 2002 with Carlo Serino [27], has improved the system⁷, basically by placing the springs (characterized by a low elastic constant) in the space of the side of the stretcher, or inside an auxiliary reinforcing stretcher [18; 14; 25]. Along with the conservation of original stretchers and the construction of new ones with unusual and unconventional sizes, we are building up a database with the chosen values of tension for the treated paintings, which will soon be published.

The introduction of Carità's tensioning systems posed a fundamental question that has not yet found a definitive answer: "what is the right level of tension for a painting mounted on an elastic stretcher?". Already in 1957 [10] objections were risen, based on the fear that the tension may overcome the painting's mechanical resistances, as it is continuous in time. Carità defended the current opinion that canvas paintings were able to withstand, and actually needed very high tensions⁸: "for tensioning a painting of a few square meters it will be necessary to use a force of nearly a ton." Nevertheless he was the first to publish the chosen value of tension, and for the detached frescoes by Cimabue from the Basilica Inferiore of St. Francesco in Assisi, he applied a force of only 136 g/cm (approx. 1,4 N/cm), very low if we consider that the weight of the artefact is of 95 g/cm on the upper margin⁹.

Unfortunately, with R. Carità's sudden departure from ICR¹⁰ (and soon after that of C. Brandi), his ideas were forgotten for many years.

The need of quantifying the forces.

The need of quantifying the forces that act in the deterioration processes of a canvas painting became a general concern when the study of the mechanical behaviour of constituent materials was started. Giovanni Urbani, in 1969 [31], proposed a research program on the mechanical aspects of conservation, and some of his points were developed and can be found in the book "Problemi di Conservazione", of 1973 [30]. The Greenwich Conference, of 1974 [33], was a fundamental moment for lining techniques, but the problem of the choice of tension was not faced¹¹.

⁶ My cooperation with Laboratorio di Restauro della Provincia di Viterbo started in January 2001, when the director Giorgio Capriotti invited me to keep a seminar workshop on the tensioning system I had published in 1996 [19]. The results of the intense work that's been carried out in 2001 were presented in the exhibition "Restaurando", 22 Dec.-13 Jan. 2002. The complete research is in [8].

⁷ Patented in 2002 by Amministrazione Provinciale di Viterbo, Antonio Iaccarino Idelson and Carlo Serino.

⁸ [10], page 168.

⁹ [10], page 170.

¹⁰ Mainly due to an accident in the financial situation of the Institute. See the interview to R. Carità in [8].

¹¹ E. Tassinari faced the problem from the point of view of the characterization of lining canvases, underlining the importance of time dependent deformations [29].

During the '80s the research crossed the ocean, as M. Mecklenburg¹² wrote his study [21] on the mechanical behaviour of the materials that build up the stratigraphy of a canvas painting. Their reaction to environmental changes was analysed regarding the stresses, dimensional changes and point of failure. He could also demonstrate that the sum of each specific tension corresponded to that of the actual painting that contained them all. Probably, the information that most influenced the general understanding of the mechanical behaviour of a canvas painting¹³ was the structural role played by animal glue at low RH values.

The choice of the value of tension.

G. Berger described in 1981 the exceptional case of the Cycloramas [6], enormous paintings (the Atlanta ones measure approx. 15 by 120 m) hung at the upper margin like a tapestry. Considering their state of conservation at different heights (and then tensions) we see that the top is the best preserved, despite the effort of carrying the weight of the whole. The reasons for this are to be found in the reduced mobility of the painting, decreasing with the distance from the constrained area, but even more in the special quality of the tension that these very strong paintings are subjected to in the upper section¹⁴: a continuous tension that is almost constant in value, as it varies only with the weight of the absorbed or desorbed moisture, thus very similar to that produced by a good elastic system.

M. Mecklenburg's data were confirmed in '88 by the studies of G. Hedley [17] and that of G. Berger and W. Russell [5]. The latter took to the general attention a relevant information, also because of the wideness of public it had reached¹⁵: in a stable environment, a raw lining canvas loses rapidly the initial tension on stretcher, until it reaches a value it can withhold in time, thus named "Maximum Sustainable Tension" (MST).

This is then a limit that should not be crossed, as the loss of tension is due to creep in the fibres. Unfortunately, MST values have not been investigated much further and, without reference values for actual paintings, the information has remained scarcely exploitable.

Alain Roche [26] demonstrated how crack formation depends on the quality (elastic or fixed) of the tension: his models on elastic stretcher have developed a hundred times less cracks than on fixed stretcher, when stressed in an environmental chamber at the same level of initial tension.

But let's step back for a moment: on which basis a restorer traditionally chooses the tension of the painting he is about to return to the owner? The ascertainment of the fact that it will inexorably loosen up, taught to use more tension than what was considered

¹² The scarce communication between the two sides of the ocean and the linguistic barriers, made the previous works of ICR, Carità, Urbani and Tassinari unknown to Mecklenburg and many others.

¹³ As P. Ackroyd underlines in [3].

¹⁴ The very important tension they are subjected to is evidently proportioned to the mechanical resistance of these special paintings.

¹⁵ This wasn't entirely new, as for instance Tassinari defined canvas elastic recover of deformation (immediate or delayed) and the limit of plastic deformation [28].

necessary, in order to keep the painting plane for a period of time long enough to avoid disputes.

Therefore, if the painting is on an elastic stretcher that keeps it constantly in the same range of tensions, the basic assumptions of the traditional choice become useless. The value of tension has to be the one that is considered suitable for the painting. But how may we define tension if not by means of its measurement? The parameters used in the traditional approach are so subjective that any comparison becomes impossible. Nevertheless, almost nobody cares to communicate the chosen value of tension, and this makes it difficult to share experiences and reproduce them. Since 1957, the papers that report this fundamental value are no more than a dozen (see Table 1).

Date	Technique	Painting and Conservator	Tension N/cm
1957	Detached fresco	Cimabue's Angels. ICR [10]	1,36
1991	Oil on canvas, lined	Caravaggio's S. Jerome. ICR [1]	6
1996	Painted and gilt leather	Leather altarpiece. ICR [23]	0,15/ 0,45
1996	Oil on canvas, lined	Decollazione Caravaggio. OPD [12]	8,5
1996	Oil on canvas, lined	Magdalena, XVII sec. Iaccarino [19]	2,6
2001	Oil on canvas, lined	Rubens Uffizi. OPD [11]	6,5
2002	Oil on canvas, lined	Three paintings, XVIII sec. Serino [27]	1,8
2003	Oil on canvas, unlined	Concave ptgs, S.D.; Equilibrarte [18]	1/ 1,5
2004	Oil on canvas, lined and unlined	6 pieces, Lab. Prov. VT, Iaccarino [8]	0,6/ 2
2004	Oil on canvas, de-lined	Boccioni. Ferriani; Equilibrarte [14]	2,1
2004	Oil on canvas, ceiling, lined	J. Miel. Rava; Equilibrarte [25]	4,4

Table 1. The published values of tension.

Ongoing research at the Conservation Laboratory of the Province of Viterbo.

In 2001 we developed several tensioning systems at the Conservation Laboratory of the Province of Viterbo¹⁶, based on R. Carità's findings. This work has made so urgent the need of choosing the value of tension on behalf of an objective, reproducible and comparable decision, that director G. Capriotti was convinced to involve the Laboratory in a research project on the balance of forces that is produced within the elastic stretcher/painting system [8].

The first step was to verify the influence of the constituent materials on the environment dependent tensions, within one of the paintings we had mounted on elastic tensioning system. The chosen painting, among the simplest from a stratigraphic point of view, has been analysed¹⁷ in order to make significant model replicas. Using a late 18th century piece of canvas, three models were prepared with increasing stratigraphy: canvas alone; sized and primed canvas; sized, primed and painted canvas. After a three months

¹⁶ See note 6.

¹⁷ See the work of Claudia Pelosi in Appendix n. 2, [8].

natural aging¹⁸, the models were mounted on elastic stretcher at 1,7 N/cm, the tension we had chosen for our painting.

Painting and replicas were conditioned at the “cautiously extreme” RH values of 30 and 87%. This allowed us to measure their overall dimensional changes, and tension they reached at equilibrium. The dimensional variation of the painting was very important, as the difference between the minimum (30% RH) and the maximum (87% RH) has been of 7 mm on a length of 130 cm (approx. 0,4%). The models’ behaviour has been coherent with that of the painting both from the qualitative and quantitative point of view, largely confirming the leading role of animal glue in the contraction and relaxation movements of the painting. Surprisingly, no humidity-related contraction of the canvas¹⁹ could be detected. As the springs have a low elastic constant, tension variation in the painting was small: starting from 1,7 N/cm, tension went to 1,85 and 1,58 N/cm. This means that the elastic system was able to keep tension within the reasonable interval of +/- approx. 7,5%.

An objective evaluation of the effects of tension

The next step was that of trying to obtain a method of evaluation of tension that, being based on its effects on the painting, could make the data comparable and reproducible.

The instinctive traditional method for tension evaluation is that of touching the painting with a hand and evaluating its deformation. A simple method could then be derived from tradition: applying a force to the centre of the painting and measuring the displacement of the corresponding area (deflection). We have then measured the Reaction to Imposed Force, and built a graph that describes, in Figure 3, the variations of the painting’s mechanical behaviour with environmental changes.

¹⁸ Artificial ageing of oil paint films, and particularly the thermal one (the easiest to produce), introduce scarcely controllable variables, as seen in [16].

¹⁹ As in the experiments of Mecklenburg, Hedley and Berger.

Figure 3. Reaction to Imposed Force of the painting on elastic stretcher, with three RH values.

The described behaviour was largely predictable on the basis of the previous tests, as the painting is more easily deformed at high RH and more rigid at low RH. The main interest of the description we find in Figure 3 is in the quantification of the effects, which enables to make comparisons with the behaviour of the painting at different tension values or with other paintings. This was first done with the same painting at a slightly higher value of tension: 2 N/cm, which is approx. 15% more than 1,7 N/cm. The new tension value made it less easily deformed at high RH, and we therefore decided to choose it for the painting, also because it “felt” suitable with the traditional hand-pressure approach.

Comparison was then done with two glue-paste lined paintings, one lined with a single canvas and the other with two. This allowed us to have a quantification of the influence of paste lining on the rigidity of the paintings. As the three paintings have different dimensions, data was corrected with a normalization factor corresponding to the dimensional ratio. Between the unlined and the double lined paintings, the difference of deflection is remarkable (the first is almost three times that of the second, as can be seen in Figure 4), while the difference between the two lined paintings is not as important. In order to have an evaluation of the influence of the number of lining canvases as related with that of the quantity of glue-paste, we introduced other normalization factors: one related to the thickness of the sandwiches, the other to their weight per surface unit. The latter brought the three curves much closer, thus indicating that the weight has a more significant influence. The differences in behaviour seem then to be due first of all to the presence or absence of a lining, and then to the weight of the sandwich built by the painting with the “roman” glue-paste technique. In this technique additional thickness is due mostly to the number of canvases, as the glue is located more in the interstices of the

canvases than between them. This therefore suggests that if weight is more important than thickness the differences are due mostly to the quantity of glue.

Figure 4. Comparison of Reaction to Imposed Force of the unlined painting with the single and double lined ones, with dimensions normalization factor. Tension on stretcher 2 N/cm, RH 55%

Figure 5. Data from figure 4, modified with the weight per surface area normalization factor.

Indirect measurement of tension

The project has developed and, after the first pioneering moment, sees today the participation of ICR²⁰, of the “Laboratory of Diagnostics for Conservation and Restoration” of University of Viterbo²¹ and of Equilibrarte s.r.l.

In order to obtain information on what conservators consider a “correct value of tension” we decided to try to measure the tension of paintings that are mounted on their original stretcher with a value that is judged correct.

The eight conservators-restorers²² of our group were asked to express their individual opinion on the tension of four paintings, that differ significantly for dimensions and conservation history, which are conserved at Town Museum of Viterbo, as can be seen in Table 2.

Name of the painting	<i>Insufficient tension</i>	<i>Adequate tension</i>	<i>Excessive tension</i>	Weight (g/m ²)	Thickness (mm)
Sacr. Polissena		7 out of 8	1 out of 8	1.209	2,4
V. Fani		6 out of 8	2 out of 8	1.356	2,2
S. Crispino		2 out of 8	6 out of 8	1.384	1,4
Ercole and Onfale	3 out of 8	4 out of 8	1 out of 8	719	1,2

Table 2. The observed value of tension, weight and thickness of paintings.

We have then tried to reconstruct the actual value of this tension (in N/cm) through RIF. The Reaction to Imposed Force was first measured for the paintings as they were in the Museum. The painting/stretcher relation was then slightly changed, in order to be able to modify and measure tension through strain gauges. In this way we could obtain a series of test data, at the same environmental conditions but with different values of tension, increased by small steps for each test repetition. The superposition of the first curve on those that corresponded to measured values of tension allowed us to measure, or rather evaluate through its effects, the tension of three out of four paintings²³, as can be seen in Table 3. These are coherent with the effects of tension we had experienced on other paintings, and well related with the values in Table 2.

Name of the painting	Evaluated tension	Measured tension	Dimensions (h x l) in cm
Sacr. Polissena	<i>Adequate, excessive rigidity due to lining</i>	3,4 N/cm	170 x 220
V. Fani	<i>Adequate</i>	1,5 N/cm	126 x 95
S. Crispino	<i>Slightly excessive</i>	2,6 N/cm	97 x 73
Ercole e Onfale	<i>Adequate, but unevenly distributed</i>	Not measured	85 x 126

Table 3. The measured value of tension, compared with the initial evaluations in table 2.

²⁰ Laboratories of Physics and of Canvas Paintings Conservation.

²¹ Dr Claudia Pelosi.

²² Linda Bernini, Giorgio Capriotti, Ottavio Di Rita, Maria Enrica Giralico, Antonio Iaccarino Idelson, Geltrude Missori, Carlo Serino, Carla Zaccheo.

²³ See [8], pages 99-109.

Towards a definition of the correct value of tension

The RIF data of the 5 paintings we studied in 2002 has taken us to the definition of a value of Maximum Useful Tension (MUT). The pattern of the graph of deflection vs. tension, at a constant deforming force, (Figure 6) is similar for all paintings even though they differ significantly for materials and dimensions.

The slope of the curve tells us that after a certain tension the painting improves much less its resistance to deformation. This means that, once reached MUT, all exceeding tensions may be considered useless for RIF and potentially dangerous for the painting.

Figure 6. The values beyond which a further increase in tension doesn't produce significant effects on the resistance to deformation of the painting, MUT. Painting: Sacrificio di Polissena, see Tables 2 and 3 (measured with the force of 8 N on the canvas).

It is then possible to try to define the **“Correct value of tension”** for a painting mounted on elastic stretcher.

Correct tension should:

- A. Keep the canvas plane, without deformations due to excessive relaxation.
- B. Be enough to provide the painting with an adequate resistance to external forces that may cause out of plane deformations.
- C. Be enough to impose a useful limit to the potentially dangerous internal stresses of the painting.
- D. Never exceed mechanical resistance of the painting, in all environmental conditions.

Programmed development of the research

The goal is that of defining more precisely the correct value of tension, and this implies more research on real paintings and models. The use of computer simulations like FEA²⁴ would also be of great help in the prediction of the behaviour of the painting/stretcher system.

Research lines for 2005 are:

1. further investigation on MUT;
2. investigation on MST for paintings;
3. measure friction of canvas on different profiles, in order to improve stretchers' performances.

Since April 2004, we have started to take a census of the value of tension that Conservators choose for a sample painting mounted on a measuring stretcher. Until January 2005 we have interviewed 98 Italian Conservators, and collected data on their education, experience, age, gender, geographical area of interest and number of paintings treated per year.

Equilibrarte (and the colleagues we work with²⁵), together with the Laboratorio di Restauro della Provincia di Viterbo are collecting a data base on the treated paintings and the chosen value of tension, that shall soon be published.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] Accardo, G.; Bennici, A.; Torre, M., "Tensionamento controllato della tela". in: AA. VV., *Il S. Gerolamo del Caravaggio a Malta dal furto al restauro*. I.C.R. 1991.
- [2] Accardo, G.; Santucci, G.; Torre, M. "Sollecitazioni meccaniche nei dipinti su tela: ipotesi su alcuni metodi di analisi e di controllo". *Atti della Conferenza Internazionale Prove Non Distruttive*, Viterbo 1992.
- [3] Ackroyd, P., "The structural conservation of canvas paintings: changes in attitude and practice since the early 1970s". In *Reviews in Conservation*, Number 3, 2002 pp. 3-14.
- [4] Berger, G. A., "A structural solution for the preservation of canvas paintings". In *Studies in Conservation*, n. 29, 1984.
- [5] Berger, G. A., Russell, W. H., "An evaluation of the preparation of canvas paintings using stress measurements". In: *Studies in Conservation*, n. 33, 1988.
- [6] Berger, G. A., "The role of tension in the preservation of canvas paintings: a study of panoramas". *ICOM CC meeting preprints*, Ottawa 81/2/3, 1-12. 1981.
- [7] Bracco, P.; Ciappi, O., ""The beheading of the Baptist" by Caravaggio. The artist's techniques, its state of conservation, its restoration". In *The return of Caravaggio's "The beheading of the Baptist" to Malta*, National Museum of Fine Arts, Valletta June 1999.

²⁴ As in [13; 20; 2; 22].

²⁵ Some collaborations are in [18; 14; 25].

- [8] Capriotti, G.; Iaccarino Idelson, A., a cura di, *Tensionamento dei dipinti su tela*. Nardini, Firenze 2004.
- [9] Carità, R., "Il restauro dei dipinti caravaggeschi della cattedrale, della Valletta a Malta". In *Bollettino dell'Istituto Centrale per il Restauro* n. 29, 1957.
- [10] Carità, R., "Aggiunta sui telai per affreschi trasportati". In *Bollettino dell'Istituto Centrale per il Restauro*, n. 31-32, 1957.
- [11] Cianfanelli, M.; Ciani Passeri, F.; Ramat, A., "Intervento di restauro". In: *Rubens agli Uffizi. Il restauro delle storie di Enrico IV*. Opificio delle Pietre Dure. Firenze EDIFIR 2001 p. 85.
- [12] Ciappi, O.; Ciatti, M., "La conservazione dei dipinti su tela: esperienze ed innovazioni". *OPD Restauro* n. 8, 1996 p. 161.
- [13] Colville, J.; Kilpatrick, W.; Mecklenburg M. F., "A finite element analysis of multi-layered orthotropic membranes with application to oil paintings on fabric". *IIC Congress Preprints* 1982.
- [14] Cremonesi, P.; Ferriani, B.; Iaccarino Idelson, A.; Serino, C.; Pugliese, M., "De-restoration and mechanical conservation of a canvas painting by Boccioni". *IIC Congress Preprints* 2004, page 222.
- [15] Del Zotto, F.; Tonini, F., "Il restauro dei dipinti del Santuario di Ribis", in AA.VV. *Il culto della Madonna nel Rojale*, Udine pp. 83-92 1988
- [16] Erhardt, D.; Tumosa, C. S.; Mecklenburg, M. F., "Natural and Accelerated Thermal Aging of Oil Paint Films". In *IIC Congress Preprints*, pp. 65-69, 2000.
- [17] Hedley, G., "Relative Humidity and the stress/strain response of canvas paintings: uniaxial measurements of naturally aged samples". *Studies in Conservation* n.33 1988.
- [18] Iaccarino Idelson, A.; Balderi, S.; Frati, D.; Serino, C., "Un intervento innovativo per dipinti su tela con telaio concavo. Riflessioni sull'uso della tensione". *Atti del Congresso dell'IG-IIC*, Giugno 2003 pp. 422-433.
- [19] Iaccarino, A. "Dipinti su tela, una proposta per conservare i telai originali". *Materiali e Strutture*, anno VI, numero 2, 1996.
- [20] Mecklenburg, M. F. (ed.), "Art in Transit: studies in the transport of paintings". Washington, DC. National Gallery of Art, 1991.
- [21] Mecklenburg, M. F., "Some aspects of mechanical behaviour of fabric supported canvas paintings", National Museum Act, 1982, non pubblicata.
- [22] Mecklenburg, M. F.; Mc Cormick-Goodhart, M.; Tumosa, C.S., "Investigation into the deterioration of paintings and photographs using computerized modelling of stress development". *Journal of the American Institute for Conservation*, n. 33, 1994 pp. 153-170.
- [23] Nimmo, M.; Paris, M.; Rissotto, L.; Bonetti, F.; Cappa, P., "Tensioning gilded and painted leather". *ICOM CC meeting preprints*, 1996 pp. 751-758.
- [24] Paris, M.; Nimmo, M.; Rissotto, L.; Cappa, P.; Bonetti, F.; Silvestri, S., "Tensionamento controllato per dipinti su cuoio: dati sperimentali". In *Bollettino dell'Istituto Centrale per il Restauro*, n. 4, 2002, pagg. 84-101.
- [25] Rava, A.; Serino, C.; Iaccarino Idelson, A., "Restauro del grande dipinto di J. Miel nel soffitto della Sala del Trono della Regina del Palazzo Reale di Torino". *Atti del Congresso dell'IG-IIC*, Settembre 2004.
- [26] Roche, A., "L'influence du type de châssis sur le vieillissement mécanique d'une peinture sur toile". *Studies in Conservation* n. 38, 1993 pp. 17-24.

- [27] Serino, C.; Serino, M., "Un nuovo telaio elastico per i dipinti su tela". *Kermes* anno 15 n. 45, 2002 pp. 45-48.
- [28] Tassinari, E., "Studio preliminare sul tensionamento delle tele di rifodero". in: Urbani, G., a cura di, *Problemi di Conservazione*. pp. 9-20. ed. Compositori, Bologna, 1973.
- [29] Tassinari, E., "Characterization of lining canvases", In Villers, C., a cura di, *Lining Paintings: Papers from the Greenwich Conference on Comparative Lining Techniques*. Archetype, Londra 2003.
- [30] Urbani, G., a cura di, *Problemi di Conservazione*. pp. 9-20. ed. Compositori, Bologna, 1973.
- [31] Urbani, G. "Propositions pour un programme de recherche sur la conservation des peintures sur toile". ICOM-CC meeting 1969.
- [32] Verougstraete-Marq, H. ; Van Schoute, R., *Cadres et supports dans la peinture flamande aux 15e et 16e siècles*. Heure le Romain: H. Verougstraete-Marcq, 1989.
- [33] Villers, C., a cura di, *Lining Paintings: Papers from the Greenwich Conference on Comparative Lining Techniques*. Archetype, Londra 2003.